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The representation of biodiversity in integrated assessment models: state of the art and directions for improvement

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E-mail: cindy.azuero@cmcc.it**Keywords:** biodiversity, IAMs, modeling, ecosystem services, climate change mitigation, reviewSupplementary material for this article is available [online](#)Original content from this work may be used under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 licence](#).

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Abstract

The biodiversity loss and climate change crises are deeply interlinked. Improving the representation of biodiversity in integrated assessment models (IAMs) is key to bridging climate change mitigation and biodiversity conservation policy. Reviewing 38 studies (2006–2025) that have incorporated biodiversity into IAMs, we identify two different paradigms. On one hand, the use of biodiversity indicators dominates the literature, using spatially explicit models that post-process IAM results and focus on habitat loss and climate change impacts globally. These studies assess how different socio-economic scenarios impact biodiversity. On the other hand, scarcer literature examines how climate-driven biodiversity loss affects human well-being. These studies use damage functions to endogenize how ecosystem service degradation affects the economy on a global scale. From this analysis, we propose that these two approaches should reconcile, by better representing biodiversity-to-economy feedbacks, or by using spatial data and biodiversity indicators. Overall, all IAMs should also improve the representation of freshwater and marine ecosystems. We provide methodological approaches for bidirectional ecosystem-economy integration. Enhancing biodiversity representation in IAMs will enable more comprehensive policy scenarios for both biodiversity conservation and climate change mitigation, while providing a more realistic representation on limits and co-benefits for climate policy.

1. Introduction

Humans are facing both climate change and an increasing and unprecedented biodiversity loss (Díaz *et al* 2019, Ceballos *et al* 2020). While strictly interconnected, potential solutions and research to support decision-making for these crises have been mainly developed independently. Ferreira *et al* (2018), Pörtner *et al* (2021, 2023), WWF (2022) have emphasized the importance of addressing both problems simultaneously to endorse synergies and co-benefits, understand trade-offs, and avoid solving one problem at the expense of the other.

Integrated assessment models (IAMs) for climate change are defined by Weyant (2017) as ‘any model that covers the whole world and, at a

minimum, includes some key elements of climate change mitigation and climate impacts systems at some level of aggregation’. First developed in the 1980 s for climate and energy policy (Meller *et al* 2015b, Bosetti 2021), IAMs have become important modeling tools for climate policy-making by evaluating future scenarios based on varying socioeconomic assumptions, technological developments, international cooperation levels, and effective implementation of mitigation actions. IAMs integrate detailed system-specific sub-models, via a soft or a hard link, representing the complex interconnections between biophysical and socioeconomic subsystems. These sub-models typically include climate models, land-use change models, energy system models, and economic models. IAMs have significantly contributed

to climate change mitigation and adaptation policy analysis, but so far have not contributed much to biodiversity conservation.

However, due to their integrated, interdisciplinary nature, and their ability to represent both the direct and indirect effects of policies (Harfoot *et al* 2013), IAMs are increasingly recognized as a key tool for bridging the gap between climate change mitigation and biodiversity conservation policy evaluation. Pereira *et al* (2010), Mace *et al* (2018) have mentioned how representing ecological processes and biodiversity indicators into IAMs—as well as the feedbacks between climate change, biodiversity and socioeconomic factors—is an improvement for better informing policies aimed at reversing biodiversity loss. Specifically, this could enhance our understanding of potential trade-offs and synergies between policies targeting biodiversity loss and climate change mitigation.

On one side, there is concern that some technological solutions for climate change mitigation could be evaluated without adequate consideration of their potential negative impacts on biodiversity (e.g. BECCS (Gough *et al* 2018, Giuntoli *et al* 2022)). Similarly, certain nature-based solutions—such as afforestation and ecosystem restoration—may be undervalued if their contributions to ecosystem health and the provision of ecosystem services are not properly considered (Seddon *et al* 2021). Conversely, omitting planned biodiversity conservation policies, such as expanding protected areas, may produce inconsistent scenarios where land is allocated to multiple incompatible uses (e.g. both protected areas and bioenergy plantations). Therefore, improving the representation of biodiversity in IAMs is a methodological contribution that will allow for a more comprehensive analysis of future policies under different climate change mitigation and biodiversity conservation pathways.

Previous reviews have analyzed how the linkages and feedback mechanisms between the economy and ecosystems have been integrated. Some studies have offered a broad overview of various modeling approaches that attempt this integration (Johnson *et al* 2025) without delving specifically into IAMs implementation. Others have focused exclusively on bioenergy impacts on biodiversity (Meller *et al* 2015b) or have outlined future research agendas for integrated social-economic-ecological modeling (Rosa *et al* 2020). In contrast, our review specifically contributes by describing and categorizing the current modeling integration of biodiversity in IAMs, explicitly distinguishing between model categories (Detailed-process and Reduced-form IAMs) and according to five clear dimensions of integration (biodiversity representation, impact drivers assessed, modeling approach, integration level, and spatial scale). Additionally, we propose practical methodological approaches to address the identified gaps.

This contributes to establishing a clearer understanding of the differences in the existing implementation methods, identify areas for improvement within each model category, and highlight opportunities to build on existing developments. In this way, with this article we aim to answer the following questions: (i) How and to what extent has biodiversity been incorporated into IAMs?, (ii) What are the key modeling gaps? and (iii) How can this representation be improved? Ultimately, with this review we do not intend to determine whether representing biodiversity in IAMs is the only or most effective way to capture the interplay between climate change and biodiversity in an integrated model. We neither intend to describe the state of the art in the literature in modeling biodiversity, ecosystem services or their interconnections.

The paper is organized as follows. First, we describe the state of the art concerning the representation of biodiversity in IAMs, including existing modeling gaps. Second, we describe different methodologies that can be used to fully integrate biodiversity into IAMs. Finally, we discuss limitations and future research directions.

2. The current representation of biodiversity in IAMs

2.1. Methodology to review the literature

2.1.1. What are IAMs and how different types have different biodiversity representations.

IAMs are defined by Weyant (2017) as ‘any model that covers the whole world and, at a minimum, includes some key elements of climate change mitigation and climate impacts systems at some level of aggregation.’

There is a great variety of models fitting this definition, differing on the modeling detail, components and research applications. Consequently various classifications of IAMs have been created. Among all possible classifications, we use that of *Detailed-process IAMs* and *Reduced-form IAMs*, which is a mix of the one described by Gambhir *et al* (2019) and that commonly used by the IAM community (Weyant 2017, Bosetti 2021). This classification is particularly relevant for examining different biodiversity representations in IAMs. The classification is not always clean-cut; some models blur the lines between categories or have evolved over time to incorporate features of both. More information on IAMs and their classifications can be found in (Weyant 2017, Bosetti 2021).

Reduced-form IAMs, also known as Benefit-Cost IAMs or climate IAMs, have highly aggregated and simplified representations of relationships between economic growth, emissions, mitigation costs, and climate impacts. These IAMs typically compare the benefits of avoiding climate change impacts with mitigation costs, to identify the ‘optimal’ level of climate mitigation. Results from these models are most commonly reported in IPCC WGII reports focusing

on climate change impacts. Examples of this type of IAMs include DICE (Nordhaus 2008, Hänsel *et al* 2020), RICE (Nordhaus and Yang 1996), FUND (Tol 1997, Anthoff and Tol 2008), and MIMOSA (van der Wijst *et al* 2021). Regarding biodiversity, due to the type of questions historically answered by Reduced-form IAMs and its highly aggregated representation, the interest has been in analyzing *which are the impacts on human well-being of climate change-induced biodiversity loss*. For example, which are the economic costs incurred by society from climate change altering the spatial distribution of ecosystems?

Detailed-process IAMs, also known as Full-scale IAMs or Comprehensive IAMs, typically have detailed representations of energy systems, climate mitigation technologies and land use dynamics. These models explore how to cost-effectively achieve mitigation targets, test the technical feasibility of climate policies, and assess co-benefits and trade-offs of environmental and mitigation pathways. Some have also developed cost-benefit analysis capabilities. Results from these models are most commonly reported in IPCC WGIII focusing on climate change mitigation. Examples include IMAGE (Stehfest *et al* 2014), MESSAGE-GLOBIOM (Messner and Strubegger 1995, Fricko *et al* 2017), AIM/CGE (Fujimori *et al* 2012, 2017), GCAM (Calvin *et al* 2019), REMIND-MAgPIE (Luderer *et al* 2020, Baumstark *et al* 2021), and WITCH-GLOBIOM (Emmerling *et al* 2016). Regarding biodiversity, due to the historical focus on detailed mitigation pathways, that often include both the energy and land systems, Detailed-process IAMs have focused on *which*

are the impacts on biodiversity from climate mitigation and more broadly on which are the impacts on biodiversity of different socio-economic scenarios. For example, what are the impacts on biodiversity of different mitigation pathways with varying land use change requirements and bioenergy use?

Figure 1 illustrates how structural differences and historical research questions, between the two model types, have resulted in different biodiversity representations. The figure illustrates how Detailed-process IAMs, with their detailed representation have been able to represent how different socio-economic scenarios result in drivers of biodiversity loss, which then are used to assess how these affect biodiversity. In contrast, Reduced-form IAMs, with a very aggregated representation have use simplified relationships to connect climate change impacts on ecosystems to human well-being.

The biodiversity literature on these two model types has diverged substantially; therefore, we describe the current state of the art in the representation of biodiversity by separating Detailed-process IAMs and Reduced-form IAMs. By including both in this review, we aim to identify strengths in each representation of biodiversity, that can address weaknesses identified in the gaps section.

2.1.2. Criteria to identify relevant studies.

To assess the state of the art in integrating biodiversity in IAMs, we selected studies that used or modified an IAM and explicitly expressed an intention to represent biodiversity. A model is considered an IAM in this review if it satisfies the following criteria:

1. At a minimum, the model must include endogenous climate–economic features. This means that it includes a socio–economic component, key elements of climate change mitigation (typically represented through an energy component and/or a land-use component), and a climate component that reflects the impacts of climate policy. This excludes models like GTAP-InVEST (Johnson *et al* 2023a)—classified as an IAM by Chaplin-Kramer *et al* (2024) but lacking endogenous climate feedbacks—as well as other computable general equilibrium (CGE) models such as ICES (Eboli *et al* 2010), and GTAP (Corong *et al* 2017), which similarly lack climate feedbacks.
2. It is aimed at long-term analyses, allowing dynamic interactions between socio-economic systems, climate processes, and policy interventions over time.
3. It is a computational model that uses quantitative data to resemble the real world and to run scenarios. Purely theoretical or conceptual models such as (Brøgger-Jensen *et al* 2018, Dasgupta 2021) are not included.

Global land use models such as GLOBIOM and MAGPIE are not by themselves IAMs, but one of the typical components of IAMs. When ran stand-alone, they use the same socio-economic scenarios as input and they can represent higher spatial resolutions than when fully coupled with the IAM. Because of this and considering habitat loss is the main driver of biodiversity loss, these models are highly relevant for the representation of biodiversity in IAMs. Therefore, we also included studies that used such land-use models.

The studies that explicitly expressed an intention to represent biodiversity are those that included in the title, keywords, or abstract the word ‘biodiversity’ and have indicated their aim to analyze it. This excludes papers that referred instead to more generic terms as ‘nature’, ‘ecosystems’ or ‘non-market goods’ (e.g. Drupp and Hänsel 2021). However, given the aggregated representation and terminology used by the economics of biodiversity community, we found that these strict criteria is only satisfied by two Reduced-form IAM studies. Consequently, for Reduced-form IAMs we relaxed the criteria to also incorporate papers including words such as ‘Natural Capital’ and ‘Ecological damages’.

To identify these papers, we search for literature in Google Scholar with the keywords ‘IAMs’ and ‘Biodiversity’. Considering well-known IAMs model families, we did additional searches with different IAM models names and the word ‘Biodiversity’. Finally we found some of the literature by analyzing the references of the relevant studies previously found. Our initial selection included 49 studies. We then excluded review papers, multi-model intercomparisons, and frameworks without an explicit implementation, resulting in 38 papers: 32

using Detailed-process IAMs and 6 using Reduced-form IAMs. The selected papers were published between 2006 and 2025. We supplemented this analysis with model documentation, particularly for Reduced-form IAMs. Supplementary figure S1 summarizes this process.

As indicated by our criteria, our scope focuses on the modeling representation of biodiversity in IAMs. We acknowledge the importance of second-order literature related to topics such as ecological-economic models (Tschirhart 2009), earth-economy models (Johnson *et al* 2025), Detailed-process IAMs representation of ecosystem services and other related literature. We indicate a non-exhaustive list of this literature in supplementary section S6.

2.1.3. Biodiversity implementation characteristics to describe reviewed studies.

Our analysis focuses on the implementation characteristics of biodiversity representation in each study. We identified five key characteristics to describe how biodiversity has been included in IAMs:

- *Representation of biodiversity*
- *Drivers of biodiversity loss*
- *Modeling approach*
- *Degree of integration (endogenous vs post-processed)*
- *Spatial scale*

The first characteristic examines whether *biodiversity* is explicitly represented in the study through a specific *biodiversity indicator*—such as species loss, mean species abundance (MSA), and biodiversity intactness index (BII)—or if it is represented by indirect elements such as *ecosystem services*. In the latter case, the welfare implications of biodiversity loss are assessed by estimating how ecosystem service provision is affected by economic activity, without explicitly estimating biodiversity indicators or modeling the ecological components themselves. Some studies have represented both biodiversity and ecosystem services.

The second characteristic examines which direct *drivers* of biodiversity loss are considered in the model. Direct drivers are: habitat loss and degradation, climate change, over-exploitation and unsuitable use, pollution and nutrient load, and the spread of invasive species, as described by Millenium Ecosystem Assessment (2005), OECD (2012), IPBES (2019), Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity (2020), WWF (2022)⁵.

The third characteristic refers to how the connection from the economic system to biodiversity or ecosystem services has been modeled. Some studies

⁵ Figure 2 shows the difference and relationship between direct and indirect drivers of biodiversity loss.

used a *spatial explicit approach* that relies on biodiversity models that use geographically referenced data to link drivers to biodiversity indicators. Others, used an *economic approach*, which represents biodiversity or ecosystems status with more abstract concepts such as Natural Capital degradation and damage functions. Some studies have been able to integrate both.

The fourth characteristic pertains to the degree of integration of the biodiversity dynamics in the IAM, namely, *endogenous* or *post-processed* representation. As described in figure 2, decisions made in the economic system result in drivers of biodiversity loss, which in turn affects the proper functioning of ecosystems, possibly altering the provision of ecosystem services that contribute to human well-being (Millenium Ecosystem Assessment 2005, Tschirhart 2009, Díaz et al 2018). By *endogenous representation* we refer to the fact that both the impacts of the economic system on biodiversity and the reciprocal impacts of biodiversity status on the economic system are represented in the model. In other words, an endogenous representation exists if the model incorporates a feedback mechanism that describes how

economic production affects ecosystems and how this, in turn, impacts human welfare, influencing optimal consumption and production choices. On the contrary, the *post-processing* approach only represents one direction of the link, typically how the economic system affects biodiversity, without explicitly integrating biodiversity status in the model's allocation decisions.

The fifth characteristic refers to the scale of analysis. This includes the geographical coverage of the analysis, meaning *local*, *regional* or *global*. While IAMs are global in coverage, some models have been used to analyze regional policy. Also, for spatial explicit models, this characteristic describes the spatial resolution of the modeling effort.

We use these five characteristics to describe the current state of the art of the integration of biodiversity into IAMs. We do this with a clear distinction between Detailed-process IAMs and Reduced-form IAMs. A summary of the results can be found in figure 3. The details on the studies included and the assigned classification for each of these five characteristics can be found in the supplementary information.

2.2. Detailed-process IAMs, the impacts on biodiversity of socio-economic scenarios

Here we describe the studies that have analyzed the impacts on biodiversity of different socio-economic scenarios. From the literature considered, we found and analyze 32 studies in this category. The studies analyzed include the Detailed-process IAMs: IMAGE, BLUES, MAGNET, MESSAGE, AIM, GCAM, POLES, REMIND, and its associated land use models: GLOBIOM and MAGPIE. 16 of the studies have used IMAGE.

For Detailed-process IAMs, currently, there is no model or study that has fully integrated or endogenized biodiversity. In the existing work with Detailed-process IAMs, the representation of biodiversity has been limited to only one direction, that from the economic system to ecosystems in the form of ex-post or post-processing analysis. A special case is Pamuk *et al* (2023) which uses the MAGNET model to represent the other direction, i.e. how losing ecosystem services, in particular pollination, could impact the economy. In the post-processing analysis from the economy to ecosystems, the outcomes of IAMs have been used as inputs to different biodiversity models to estimate a diverse set of biodiversity indicators. The aim, as described by Pereira *et al* (2010), IPBES (2016), Kim *et al* (2018) is to analyze biodiversity impacts for different future socio-economic scenarios. The analysis of these scenarios could support policy in distinct stages: agenda setting, design, implementation and review. This, using exploratory, target-seeking scenarios, policy-screening scenarios, and scenarios for retrospective policy evaluation, respectively.

For biodiversity, the first set of scenarios were exploratory ones, using the millennium ecosystem assessment scenarios, the SRES scenarios developed by the IPCC or OECD scenarios. These scenarios stated different futures with an extrapolation of past trends and new assumptions (IPBES 2016). Examples include (van Vuuren *et al* 2006, Eggers *et al* 2009, Hellmann and Verburg 2010, Visconti *et al* 2011, Meller *et al* 2015a). All of these studies assessed biodiversity impacts due to habitat loss, with only van Vuuren *et al* (2006) analyzing both climate change and habitat loss. All have used a spatially explicit approach on a post-processing basis. The majority of these studies (3 of 5) had a regional or local spatial scale, particularly focused in the EU and the bioenergy policy. A particular case is that of Wu *et al* (2019) which used the AIM/CGE, AIM/PLUM and AIM/BIO to impose spatially explicit derived biodiversity protection levels, using protected areas and a biodiversity index, to evaluate changes in the global biomass bioenergy potential under different levels of bioenergy protection.

Then, with the aim of understanding the consequences of climate change mitigation pathways on biodiversity, the RCP-SSP scenarios (Riahi *et al* 2017) were considered. In various cases, the land cover results compiled in the Land Use Harmonization (LUH2) project (Hurtt *et al* 2020) were used. Examples assessing RCP-SSP scenarios include (Jantz *et al* 2015, Newbold *et al* 2015, 2016, Visconti *et al* 2016, Chaudhary and Mooers 2018, Hill *et al* 2018, Hof *et al* 2018, Di Fulvio *et al* 2019, Di Marco *et al* 2019, Luderer *et al* 2019, Ohashi *et al* 2019, Powers

and Jetz 2019, Baisero *et al* 2020, Schipper *et al* 2020, Schulze *et al* 2020, Hanssen *et al* 2021, Oliveira Fiorini *et al* 2023). Another case, concentrated on scenarios with various degrees of BECCS and afforestation is that of Hirata *et al* (2024). These analyses have been concentrated on the habitat loss driver, associated with land use change, with only (Ohashi *et al* 2019, Hirata *et al* 2024) considering both the impacts due to climate change and habitat loss. One of the major results of this literature is that standard climate change mitigation scenarios could further increase biodiversity loss, because of increasing land use for biomass production. A model intercomparison of projections of biodiversity and ecosystem services (BES-SIM) using LUH2 land cover projections and RCP-SSP scenarios has been done following (Kim *et al* 2018) protocol. In the synthesis paper, (Pereira *et al* 2024), the authors found that (1) if both land use change and climate change continue, the future rate of biodiversity loss per decade could become steeper in comparison to historical (20th century) rates, (2) that historically there has been an increase in the provisioning ecosystem services with a decline in regulating ecosystem services and that trends are projected to continue in the next decades, and (3) that the fossil fuel scenario (SSP5-RCP8.5) is worse for biodiversity whereas regional rivalry (SSP3-RCP6.0) is worse for ecosystem services. Another approach assessing different mitigation scenarios is that of Tokimatsu *et al* (2020) who focuses on the methodological integration between IAMs and LCA (using the LIME model) to assess changes in environmental impacts, including biodiversity impacts due to both habitat loss and climate change derived from a spatial explicit analysis.

As a response to the previous literature and from the need to use IAMs to also support conservation policy, a third wave of research has started to design and evaluate scenarios aiming at reducing future biodiversity loss (Leclere *et al* 2020, Veerkamp *et al* 2020, Kok *et al* 2023), or to address the two issues simultaneously (von Jeetze *et al* 2023, Ambrósio *et al* 2024). This set of studies has identified that it is possible to bend the curve on biodiversity loss, while meeting other targets (e.g. food security, and climate change mitigation), but unprecedented action and coordination are required to do so.

Overall, as can be seen in figure 3 and table S2, most of the papers analyzed (84%) have represented only biodiversity, with a few examples that have considered both biodiversity and ecosystem services. From the ones including ecosystem services, all have represented provisioning services, in particular timber. Veerkamp *et al* (2020), Kok *et al* (2023) are the only ones also including regulating services. von Jeetze *et al* (2023) is the only one that represented only ecosystem services, including pollination sufficiency, soil erosion, biological pest control, material production, and climate regulation.

Table 1. Spatial resolution of spatially explicit approaches estimated biodiversity indicators. Pamuk *et al* (2023) was not considered in this table. Total number of studies: 31.

Aprox. Spatial resolution (m)	Number of studies	% of total studies
300	2	6%
500	1	3%
1000	5	16%
10 000	5	16%
30 000	4	13%
50 000	11	35%
200 000	1	3%
NA ^a	2	6%

^a EU NUTS2 and economic regions.

Regarding drivers of biodiversity loss, no representation of pollutants, invasive species or over-exploitation is present. All papers focus on habitat loss instead, which is the only driver represented for 45% of the analyzed papers. About 48% also included climate change. The only biodiversity model that accounts for a comprehensive list of biodiversity loss drivers is the GLOBIO model (Schipper *et al* 2020), and when connected to IMAGE as in Schipper *et al* (2020), Kok *et al* (2023) or Ambrósio *et al* (2024) (that uses the GLOBIO emulator), results in three of the only examples using Detailed-process IAMs on a post-processing basis that accounts for more than two drivers of biodiversity loss. The fourth one is Luderer *et al* (2019) which has used a life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) approach using the THEMIS model and ReCiPe database.

All papers in this Detailed-process IAMs category have used a spatially explicit approach with different levels of resolution ranging from 30 m to 200 km (See table 1). We provide details on biodiversity indicators in figure 4(a) and table S3, while we show information on biodiversity models in figure 4(b) and table S4. We constructed these figures and tables considering that each study could have estimated more than one indicator (14 of the 31 studies that estimated biodiversity indicators- see table S5), one model can be used to estimate several indicators, and one indicator can be estimated by various models. The total number of indicators estimated in these 31 studies is 54. We did not include in the tables the 32th study analyzed in this review section (Pamuk *et al* 2023), because it does not estimate a biodiversity indicator.

Regarding the biodiversity indicators used, the three most common are species richness with 33%, followed by suitable area indicators (e.g. extent of suitable habitat (ESH), area of habitat (AOH), etc) with 17%, and population's abundance indicators (e.g. MSA, BII (Scholes and Biggs 2005) or total abundance) with a sum of 24%. About biodiversity models, and following (Kim *et al* 2018) classification, community-based models are more common than

Figure 4. Biodiversity indicators (panel (a)) and models (panel (b)) used by the 31 Detailed-process IAMs studies estimating biodiversity indicators. 14 of the studies used more than one indicator, the categories in biodiversity indicator and biodiversity models are not mutually exclusive. Total number of studies analyzed: 31, Total number of indicators estimated: 54. A study could have estimated one or more indicators, could have used the same model for more than one indicator, and could have more than one indicator under the same indicator subcategory. ESH: extent of suitable habitat, AOH: area of habitat.

species-based models. From the community-based models, the most common approach is to estimate a statistical model using the PREDICTS database (Hudson *et al* 2014, 2017, Purvis *et al* 2018), followed by SAR models (Pereira and Daily 2006, Proença and Pereira 2013, Pereira *et al* 2014) and GLOBIO (Alkemade *et al* 2009, Schipper *et al* 2020). From the species-based models, habitat suitability models are the most used approaches, followed by species distribution models (SDMs), other statistical models and GLOBIO-Species.

Table S1 provides additional information about each biodiversity model, including goals, subcategories, indicators each model can estimate, and examples. Figure S2 shows how different biodiversity indicators refer to different dimensions of biodiversity and/or levels of ecological organization. For further details on biodiversity models and indicators, refer to Pereira *et al* (2010), (2013), (2024), Kim *et al* (2018), Weiskopf *et al* (2022).

All of the studies, except two, have used a post-processing approach. Up to the best of our knowledge, the closest attempt to fully endogenize biodiversity in a spatially explicit manner has been (Azuero-Pedraza *et al* 2024), which has integrated a biodiversity model (the countryside species-area relationship (cSAR) model) into a land use change model (GLOBIOM-Forest), but not into the IAM itself.

The scale has been mostly global (81% of the papers analyzed), with a few regional examples such as Eggers *et al* (2009), Hellmann and Verburg (2010), Meller *et al* (2015a), Di Fulvio *et al* (2019), Veerkamp *et al* (2020), Oliveira Fiorini *et al* (2023). From the regional studies, all but one are in Europe.

For further description and analyses of the results of these post-processed approaches, the following reviews can be checked (Pereira *et al* 2010, 2024, Weiskopf *et al* 2022).

It is important to mention that all previous studies have focused on the biodiversity impacts of terrestrial ecosystems, leaving a gap in the study of freshwater and marine ecosystems in IAMs.

2.3. Reduced-form IAMs, the impacts on human well-being of biodiversity loss

Here we describe the studies that are interested in analyzing how human well-being is affected by climate change through the destruction of ecosystems and biodiversity loss.

We only identified six studies for this category. The studies analyzed encompass some of the major model families of Reduced-form IAMs. We identified two studies using FUND (Anthoff and Tol 2008, Brooks and Newbold 2014), two studies using DICE (Hackett and Moxnes 2015, Bastien-Olvera and Moore 2021), one study using RICE (Bastien-Olvera *et al* 2023), and one study using GRAPE (Kosugi *et al* 2009).

None of the analyzed models provide a spatially explicit representation of biodiversity indicators, ecosystem services or other proxies. Reduced-form IAMs have focused instead on representing ecological damages through the use of temperature-dependent damage functions aimed at capturing the feedback effects between changes in natural capital—including biodiversity and ecosystems—and the economy. Moreover, such implementation efforts remain restricted to isolated exercises and do not yet

represent stable or systematically integrated features within the models of origin.

A first attempt to include an explicit ecosystem damage function into a Reduced-form IAM was conducted using the 'Framework for Uncertainty, Negotiation, and Distribution' (FUND) model (Tol 1997, Hope 2006, Anthoff and Tol 2008), further developed by Brooks and Newbold (2014). The biodiversity implementation in FUND3.3 consists of a highly simplified biodiversity loss function that relates temperature changes to species extinction rates over time. The change in the stock of 'biodiversity' is projected at the global scale over time by calibrating temperature-related damage functions based on literature. The model then applies a biodiversity value function that converts species loss into economic damages via willingness-to-pay estimates, which are subsequently incorporated into the model's social welfare function. This approach integrates biodiversity changes into the utility function, affecting economic welfare through non-use values exclusively. The implementation only relies on biodiversity changes due to climate change impacts at an aggregate global scale without any spatial resolution.

Among the DICE family, model expansions of the standard model (Nordhaus 2008) incorporate ecological elements via the concept of Natural Capital, which represents the stock of natural resources (e.g. market goods as timber and non-market goods as climate stabilization) needed for economic activity (Costanza and Daly 1992, Barbier 2019). Under this approach, no explicit biodiversity indicator is used. Instead, the stocks of natural resources which are directly affected by climate change and economic activity are measured in monetary units, theoretically reflecting the use value of these resources for human well-being.

A first example is the DICE-NC (Hackett and Moxnes 2015). It expands the original model by introducing a natural capital variable that is affected by both climate change and the depletion effects of economic activity, and that represents biotic and abiotic resource stocks and systems. Both the original DICE production function and damage-response functions are not directly affected by natural capital loss. The feedback effect on welfare is therefore modeled by introducing a cost multiplier to the net output for natural capital degradation. However, no empirical justification is provided for the data used for the calibration of relevant equations. Parameters like the initial degradation intensity or recovery rate are presented as illustrative assumptions rather than empirically grounded estimates.

GREEN DICE, developed by Bastien-Olvera and Moore (2021), extended the DICE model by including both representations of use and non-use values of terrestrial ecosystems. To do so, in addition to explicitly modeling climate damages to the natural capital stock through a damage function, they modified the

utility functions of consumers to depend on 1) normal consumption goods, 2) ecosystem services (non-market goods such as recreation or cultural values), and 3) existence and bequest values. Elasticities are assigned without empirical evidence and evaluated via sensitivity analysis.

A similar model, but with regional representation is RICE. Bastien-Olvera *et al* (2023) used an extended version of RICE50+ (Gazzotti *et al* 2021) to estimate the effect of changing natural capital on the market and non-market benefits, called GREEN RICE. This is an improvement compared with previous implementations of Natural Capital since it uses dynamic global vegetation models to estimate area shifts in terrestrial biomes as a response to climate change in a spatial explicit manner. Country-level estimates of natural capital (market and non-market) as a share of total wealth were derived from World Bank national accounts data, allowing the authors to quantify the relative contribution of each biome to these benefits.

In this way, current implementations of biodiversity in the DICE/RICE family represent ecosystem services using Natural Capital as a proxy. Damages are driven by climate change, and modeled with an economic approach by endogenizing the impacts of changes in ecosystem services on the global economy, affecting the model's final output and/or the utility of consumers. Only (Bastien-Olvera *et al* 2023) also includes a spatially explicit estimation of the climate change impacts on ecosystems, and calibrates the damage functions with real-world data. Still, none of the studies analyzed uses biodiversity indicators.

A different approach from Kosugi *et al* (2009) integrates GRAPE (a DICE-based reduced-form IAM) with the LIME LCIA model, to replace the aggregated damage function linking temperature with GDP with an environmental impact module. This module estimates the physical impacts from GHG emissions, SOx emissions, and land use change on four endpoints (human health, social welfare, biodiversity, and primary productivity), which are then monetized and subtracted from GDP. Due to data limitations, this version represents only land-use-driven biodiversity impacts on a 10-regions resolution. This methodological integration has been further developed by Tokimatsu and Yasuoka (2024).

Overall, as can be seen in figure 3 and table S6, there are two types of studies for Reduced-form IAMs. Those that directly assessed biodiversity loss (as Kosugi *et al* (2009), Brooks and Newbold (2014)), and those that focused on natural capital, which are primarily oriented toward ecosystem services loss. Similarly, with the exception of Kosugi *et al* (2009), the only impact driver represented is climate change, whose effects are proxied by temperature change. We defined the implementation approaches used as economic approach, meaning that some economic valuation, natural capital and damage functions are implemented in Reduced-form

Table 2. Use and non-use values included in BC-IAMs. Total number of studies analyzed: 5. Each study could have incorporated more than one value category. Kosugi *et al* (2009) is not included in this table since it does not represent ecosystem services nor non-use values.

Component of human valuation	Number of studies	% of total studies
Provisioning ES	3	60%
Supporting ES	2	40%
Regulating ES	2	40%
Cultural ES	1	20%
Non-Use	3	60%

IAMs to model the link between the economic system and the biodiversity/ecosystem services loss. Due to the interest in analyzing the impacts on human well-being, these models have also used these more abstract concepts to reduce the models' final output and/or utility to consumers as a response to ecological damage. This is meant to endogenously represent both the impacts of the economic system on biodiversity (or its proxies) and the reverse feedback on economic system. Most studies use aggregated data on a global level with no spatial resolution. Only (Bastien-Olvera *et al* 2023) provides a spatial explicit estimation of biomes shift at ~ 55 km ($0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$).

Moreover, in table 2 we show that both use and non-use values of ecosystems have been represented, with 3 of 5 papers representing provisioning ecosystem services.

3. Current modeling gaps

3.1. About estimating biodiversity impacts

Biodiversity indicator limitations Due to the complexity and multidimensionality of the biodiversity concept (IPBES 2019), and because of the differences in how fast indicators respond to global change (Pereira *et al* 2010), experts have recommended that more than one indicator should be used to assess the status of biodiversity. Even so, half of the studies done with biodiversity models, in Detailed-process IAMs, only used one biodiversity indicator as can be seen in table S5.

Moreover, Reduced-form IAMs have no explicit estimation of biodiversity indicators. Most rely on ecosystem services or natural capital proxies that do not necessarily intend to only represent biodiversity, and the ones that do, associated with the FUND model, only used species richness as an indicator.

Ecosystem services and biodiversity are related but distinct concepts that require their own indicators. Relying solely on ecosystem service indicators, when trying to represent biodiversity, risks protecting only ecosystems with established economic value, thereby misaligning with conservation goals. Conversely, biodiversity indicators only focused on rare or endangered species do not necessarily capture changes in the provision of ecosystem services.

Incomplete coverage of biodiversity loss drivers

Not all direct drivers of biodiversity loss have been represented (see figure 3). In particular, there is a lack of representation of pollutants, invasive species, and over-exploitation in all IAMs. Moreover, Reduced-form IAMs have two key limitations: they proxy climate change using only mean temperature, and they omit human-induced land-use change entirely. The former ignores climate change-related pressures beyond temperature, including precipitation changes, extreme events, droughts, pests, and fire.

Limitations in spatial representations

A spatial explicit representation of biodiversity and ecosystem services is essential to capture regional differences in impacts. Aggregated resolutions typically hide local changes most relevant for policy and ecosystems. In Detailed-process IAMs, that already incorporate land use systems, their aggregated resolution limits its ability to capture local and landscape-level opportunities and constraints that are important to assess and mitigate biodiversity impacts (Meller *et al* 2015b). In this regard, when integrating biodiversity into IAMs there is still a challenge due to the mismatch in the spatial resolution between land use models, IAMs, and biodiversity models, that has so far limited most of the couplings with biodiversity models to a post-process exercise. This can be a limitation for integrating the feedback of biodiversity in the economy.

All except one of the studies analyzed, that used Reduced-form IAMs, lack a spatial explicit representation missing the assessment of these spatial differences.

Habitat representation beyond area

Detailed-process IAMs have successfully represented changes in habitat availability, but have missed habitat quality and structure (Meller *et al* 2015b). Reduced-form IAMs due to simplified or absent representation of land use systems, have not been coupled with any biodiversity model, and thus lack even basic habitat availability assessments.

Data availability and quality, and model uncertainty

There are limitations associated to the biodiversity models itself. In general, data quality and availability for some regions of the world are still a challenge. Similarly, biodiversity models are subject to high levels of uncertainty (Thuiller *et al* 2019), which should be considered when using future projections of indicators of biodiversity impacts.

The calibration of damage functions (both from economy to biodiversity and vice versa), is also limited by data quality and spatial coverage, which have potential effects in the robustness of the estimated relationships, potentially misrepresenting real impacts.

Ecosystems coverage Only terrestrial ecosystems have been represented, omitting the analysis of biodiversity impacts on freshwater and marine ecosystems. Harfoot *et al* (2013) describes the importance of representing the aquatic realms for its importance for food production associated with fish, and how the supply of fish has an impact on protein demand from terrestrial sources.

Overall, all these gaps limit the ability to properly assess the magnitude of biodiversity impacts, potentially underestimating them and misrepresenting spatial differences. However not all gaps are equally severe. The lack of use of spatial explicit models in Reduce-form IAMs severely limits the representation of biodiversity impacts due to habitat loss, which is the major driver of biodiversity loss. This is therefore a priority for improvement. Similarly, Detailed-process IAMs should prioritize the use of more than one biodiversity model and indicator. This will better reflect biodiversity status and help address model uncertainty. Furthermore, improving the representation of biodiversity impacts in response to pollutants and representing marine and freshwater ecosystems, is highly relevant to address potential negative effects of climate mitigation policy that cannot be addressed with current implementations. Initial efforts should focus on these key areas.

3.2. About integrating biodiversity into IAM decision-making

Missing biodiversity-to-economy feedbacks Detailed-process IAMs capture impacts on biodiversity but not feedbacks to the economy (all but one study use only a post-processing analysis). Reduced-form IAMs have represented the link, but have weak empirical support for the damage functions used, lack spatial and sectoral specificity and still struggle to represent the complex linkages between biodiversity loss, ecosystem service provision and their economic consequences resulting in various areas of improvement.

Missing this link relates to three critical limitations for research and policy evaluation. First, models can miss constraints on technology deployment and upscaling because of their direct or indirect effects on biodiversity which can lead to inconsistent policies (Meller *et al* 2015b). For example, not considering protected areas when estimating available land for climate mitigation or assuming continued ecosystem service provision despite degradation (Harfoot *et al* 2013).

Second, there is misrepresented sectoral production. Models that ignore known ecosystem service dependencies -pollinators to agriculture (Melathopoulos *et al* 2015), mangrove forests to fisheries (Barbier and Strand 1998, Getzner and Islam 2020), forest cover to water quality (Núñez *et al* 2006)- will misrepresent future production when ecosystems are damaged. Third, without bidirectional

integration, it is harder to identify co-benefits, synergies, trade-offs, win-win strategies, and conflicts between climate change mitigation and biodiversity goals, hindering action prioritization and risk management.

Calibration and valuation challenges This problem is particular to Reduced-form IAMs. We identified clear gaps in the construction of the damage functions used. Most lack empirical support relying on limited literature, 'expert guesses' or sensitivity analysis to assign parameter values (e.g. as in FUND (Brooks and Newbold 2014)). Additionally, representing non-traded ecosystem services requires non-market valuation methods with well-known limitations (Diamond and Hausman 1994, Tietenberg and Lewis 2012), particularly for non-use values. Both imply a misrepresentation of the impacts of biodiversity loss to the economy, limiting the insights that can be derived from the modeling effort.

4. Methodological approaches for an improved biodiversity representation in IAMs

In this section, we concentrate on describing methodological approaches that can be used to better represent biodiversity in IAMs. Because IAMs differ in their modeling framework, structure, and status of development regarding the representation of biodiversity, instead of describing a unique methodology to represent biodiversity in IAMs, we describe various ways to do so. We separate the methodologies according to the direction of the link between biodiversity and the economic system that they intend to represent. The ideal representation of biodiversity in IAMs is one that represents both directions of this link. The methodologies we describe here consider a broader set of literature (some of them mentioned in supplementary section S6), beyond the one reviewed above. This section does not intend to be an exhaustive review of the literature on how to connect economic models with nature, ecosystems or biodiversity. Our aim is to provide guidance by describing a set of existing alternatives from which each IAM development team could choose the most appropriate approach. Some of these approaches should be considered as starting points with further developments required to address their limitations. With this description, we mean to provide practical guidance to represent biodiversity in IAMs using the current state of the art and to address several of the gaps described in previous sections. We provide a summary of the gaps identified, potential solutions, practical challenges, preconditions for implementation, and examples of existing datasets or models, discussed in this section in supplementary table S7.

4.1. From the economic system to ecosystems

On a general basis, to represent the link from the economic system to ecosystems two components must be satisfied in the IAM. First, the drivers of biodiversity loss need to be explicitly represented in the IAM. For example, the IAM needs to have as an outcome land use change decisions (for habitat loss); climate change indicators; consumption of wild animal species (for over-exploitation); and pollutants on air, soil & water. Second, a relationship between these drivers and one or more biodiversity indicators needs to be represented.

For the drivers component, most IAMs already represent land use decisions and climate change indicators. For over-exploitation and pollutants indicators, further developments in the IAMs need to be done before fully attempting to represent the biodiversity impacts due to these drivers. There has been work on including fisheries in land use models (Deppermann *et al* 2019, Spillias *et al* 2023) which could potentially be used for overexploitation. About pollutants, some pollutants from agricultural practices, such as fertilizers, can already be used. Others can be represented once current developments on materials representation in IAMs are completed. We will not concentrate on proposing how to extend IAMs so they can have more drivers as outcome variables.

We will concentrate on the second component, that of the relationship between the driver and a biodiversity indicator, by taking advantage of current modeling approaches used in IAMs. In general, there are two different ways to derive a relationship between the drivers of biodiversity loss and biodiversity indicators, the *correlative* and *process-based* models, as described by IPBES (2016). The process-based models (which include mechanistic models) attempt to explicitly model mechanisms and processes with parameters that have ecological interpretation. Instead, the correlative models do not attempt to represent explicit ecological processes and are derived using statistical methods. Depending on the driver, the current availability of each type of model differs.

For human-induced habitat loss, we can take advantage of the existing connection between IAMs and global land use change models, and between global land use change models and biodiversity models. There is a mismatch in the spatial resolution used by global land use change models and IAMs, which is particularly relevant for biodiversity impacts assessment (Meller *et al* 2015b). Considering this mismatch, high spatial resolution results from land use models are aggregated to match IAMs spatial resolution, which is usually economic regions. Given IAMs regional aggregation and the computational limitations of hard linking the full land use model, the most common approach to connect the land use system in IAMs has been with the use of emulators or response

functions, constructed with datasets such as the look-up tables⁶. These emulators are simplified mathematical functions that are included inside the IAM, which take as input variables from the IAM and return as output, variables of interest from the land use system. For example, a typical land use emulator will take as input the carbon price and the requirements for biomass and will output the GHG emissions of induced land use change and the cost of biomass production. In the case of biodiversity due to habitat loss, a similar approach can be used. This means, also creating response functions or emulators of biodiversity that are a simplification of more complex biodiversity and land use change models. To do this, look-up tables from land use change models should be extended to output an additional variable, a biodiversity indicator. Equation (1) is an example of the general functional form of a response function of biodiversity as a response to increased biomass use. In this equation, B is the biodiversity indicator and Q_{wbio} is the demanded quantity of biomass for the energy system. This relationship changes depending on the carbon price p_C .

$$B = f(Q_{wbio}|p_C) \quad (1)$$

For this implementation, land use models must be connected to a biodiversity model and provide, ideally, more than one biodiversity indicator. Leclere *et al* (2020) provides a good example of this. If updating the lookuptables is not possible, a starting approach is to estimate the biodiversity indicators using land cover outcomes at the regional resolution from the IAMs and use simplified representations, such as linear coefficients that relate biodiversity loss indicators to land cover, or emulators designed to work at the IAM regional resolution. An example of the latter is the GLOBIO MSA emulator <https://github.com/imagepbl/image-land-msa-tool> of the GLOBIO model developed by the IMAGE team at PBL (Ambrósio *et al* 2024), which is developed to be connected with the low spatial resolution of most IAMs. Although, by reducing the spatial resolution, the accuracy of biodiversity indicators may be affected.

Biodiversity impacts of climate change are complex with impacts on several levels of biological organization, from organisms to ecosystems. As described by Bellard *et al* (2012), Scheffers *et al* (2016) these impacts have been reflected in genetic, physiologic, morphologic, and phenologic⁷ changes for species, in addition to the shifting of their distributions.

⁶ Look-up tables of global land use models correspond to a dataset where several land system indicators are shown for a matrix of scenarios. This matrix usually refers to a combination of biomass prices and carbon prices. An example, for the GLOBIOM model, is described in Frank *et al* (2021).

⁷ Refers to the timing of migrations and life-processes. For example, budding and flowering in plants, hatching and fledging in birds, hibernation in mammals, spawning times in fish, and more.

Well-known examples are migration and species distribution shifts, due to increased temperatures or changes in precipitation patterns (Wiens 2016). Another example, on a physiology level for organisms, is that of temperature-dependent sex determination of marine species, as is the case of the feminization of marine turtles (Poloczanska *et al* 2009, Patrício *et al* 2021) or coral reefs with increased bleaching events due to longer periods of increased ocean temperatures (Spalding and Brown 2015). These changes can affect survival and population levels.

Regarding the relationship between the climate change driver and biodiversity indicators for model integration, models such as SDMs, habitat suitability models (HSMs), and DGVMs could be used to construct lookup-tables and response functions, as these can represent species distribution and ecosystem range changes in response to climate conditions. Practical challenges include the need and processing of data for each species analyzed, which for a global model could be a limiting factor. From the literature here analyzed, the largest number of species so far included in a HSM is 19 400 terrestrial species including amphibians, birds and mammals (Powers and Jetz 2019). For comparison, the IUCN Red List identifies 46 300 species threatened with extinction in 2025.

Given the complexity of climate change's impact on biodiversity, correlative (empirical) approaches can also be used to derive a response function based on biodiversity indicators and climate variables, similar to the damage functions in Reduced-form IAMs. Finding enough data (e.g. that allows constructing panel datasets) and facing endogeneity are important challenges to encounter with this approach. An important issue is how to disentangle the direct effects of climate change (e.g. species shifts due to temperature and precipitation) from indirect effects resulting from human-induced land use change (e.g. agricultural expansion).

For over-exploitation, fish in marine ecosystems are a good starting point. This is because fish species may be the only animal species currently represented in some IAMs, are the main example of over-exploitation, and have a clear connection with climate change mitigation. The latter through the agricultural sector, by shifting diets. If land-use models or fisheries modules provide additional outcome variables, about fish populations, these can be used to construct a response function and biodiversity indicators associated with this driver. A challenge in those fisheries' representations for the estimation of biodiversity impacts would be how to properly model the interconnections between marine species and the role of aquaculture. Indeed a precondition for this approach is to have fisheries represented and connected in a way that scenarios including shifting diets can be assessed.

Pollutants affecting biodiversity can be found in the atmosphere, dissolved in/carried by water or in the soil (IPBES 2019).

Air pollutants deposition of inorganic substances such as NO_x, SO₂ and NH₃ results in terrestrial acidification which can affect plant species (Azevedo *et al* 2013b). Photochemical-formed ozone can affect plant species by affecting growth, leaf senescence and reducing plants' abilities to withstand stressors (van Goethem *et al* 2013, van Zelm *et al* 2016).

Water pollutants associated with untreated sewage, and industrial & agricultural runoff expose ecosystems to organic pollutants, heavy metals, such as zinc, copper and aluminum, pharmaceutical residues, and surfactants, among others (IPBES 2019). In particular agricultural runoff contains pesticides, herbicides, and fertilizers. The latter resulting in freshwater eutrophication (Azevedo *et al* 2013a). There is also exposure to plastics and other compounds belonging to both the black (e.g. mercury, cadmium) and grey (e.g. arsenic, lead, copper, zinc, fluorides) lists of substances (IPBES 2019) affecting both freshwater and marine ecosystems.

Currently, the existing representation of air pollutants in IAMs can be connected with LCIA characterization factors (CFs) (Huijbregts *et al* 2017), as a starting point to represent the link between pollutants and biodiversity. Similarly, fertilizer runoff can be estimated from fertilizer use in land use models. Therefore, using fertilizer data from land use models to estimate phosphorus concentrations in freshwater ecosystems and linking these concentrations to biodiversity indicators (as in Azevedo *et al* 2013a), an initial representation between pollutants and biodiversity can be done in IAMs. Still using CFs do not represent the non-linear responses of biodiversity to pollutants and the potential disappeared fraction of species (PDF) biodiversity indicator, if used alone, is limited to assess biodiversity status.

In general, due to the complexity and multidimensionality of biodiversity, it is advised to produce more than one biodiversity indicator when representing the link from the economic system to biodiversity. In practice, using indicators that represent different dimensions is recommended. For example, one population-based indicator (e.g. MSA, BII, LPI), and one species-based indicator (e.g. species richness, PDF, red list index, ESH) could be used. These are indicators already being calculated in the existing literature. For future improvement, ecosystem health indicators (Rowland *et al* 2019) could also be considered. Similarly, functional diversity (Mace *et al* 2014, Scherer *et al* 2020) indicators can be useful when connecting with ecosystem services. Using more than one indicator (and more than one biodiversity model) is also helpful to address the limitation of data quality, availability, and uncertainty of biodiversity models

(Thuiller *et al* 2019). An important caveat is that various of the existing biodiversity indicators and models have an inherent linearity, assuming the same marginal change in biodiversity status independent on how intact the ecosystem is.

As described before, a challenge is the difference in spatial scales between IAMs, and biodiversity models. This is a practical challenge for modeling purposes, that can be addressed in two ways. The first, described before, refers to *aggregating* results from a higher spatial resolution to a lower spatial resolution, as the response functions' approach used for the habitat loss driver. This allows us to represent all spatial considerations and trade-offs when estimating biodiversity indicators. A second approach is to *disaggregate* IAMs results using downscaling tools such as SEALS (Suh *et al* 2020) or AIM/PLUM (Hasegawa *et al* 2017), and then use the higher resolution outputs with biodiversity models. Which approach to use depends on the research question and each model capabilities. In general the former is more useful for fully representing the link between biodiversity and the economic systems, whereas the latter is more useful for assessing local, and landscape opportunities on a post-processing basis. A more detailed discussion describing the spatial scale challenges when integrating local and global dimensions for sustainability modeling can be found in Johnson *et al* (2023b).

Further on, the representation of freshwater and marine ecosystems- and its associated biodiversity impacts- in IAMs should be improved. In practice, defining spatial boundaries may be a challenge. Not only there are areas of the ocean that do not belong to a particular country, but also there are deep ocean ecosystems still being understood. Also, rivers may share boundaries with different countries and the impacts on ecosystems from a driver upstream may be seen downstream. These characteristics result in practical limitations with spatial data and when defining boundaries for model representation. Indeed for marine and freshwater ecosystems representation to be relevant for scenarios, drivers that affect them need to be represented in IAMs. Starting points for improvement are fisheries, as done by Deppermann *et al* (2019), Spillias *et al* (2023), and more correlative approaches as BLUE RICE (Bastien-Olvera *et al* 2026) that included coral reefs, mangrove forests and fisheries.

4.2. From ecosystems to the economic system

The aim of representing the link from biodiversity to the economic system is to close the loop, for an integrated decision making. This raises the question of how biodiversity affects the economic system, and why and how it should be modeled, a topic with a broader set of literature not exhaustively reviewed here. Each conceptualization of biodiversity role translates to different integrations of biodiversity into the economic system. We describe different

modeling approaches that can be implemented in IAMs, along with some of the underlying assumptions regarding biodiversity's value and role in the economic system, without prescribing a single best approach.

From a mathematical optimization perspective, there are two general methods to represent the link from ecosystems to the economic system once the IAM can estimate one or more biodiversity indicators. The first method is to use the biodiversity indicator directly and impose a hard constraint. This can be considered a sustainability limit type of representation. This could be useful for scenarios, targets, or command and control type of policies. A practical challenge with this implementation is how to determine the limit. If there is no policy with a predefined target, sensibility analysis and scenarios on the selected limit should be done. Similarly, imposing a hard constraint can have significant effects on model feasibility. Incorporating biodiversity in this way into the economic system limits the trade-off between biodiversity and other variables of interest, in a sense, the level chosen represents the level of substitutability attributed to biodiversity in comparison to other outcomes of the economic system.

The second approach makes this substitutability, and therefore the possibility to trade-off biodiversity with other economic outcomes, more flexible. In this approach, the biodiversity indicator is explicitly connected to the economic system letting the economic agents decide on biodiversity loss considering the benefits of having biodiversity (or the costs of losing it). From a modeling perspective, the biodiversity indicator can be linked to the economic system in four ways, (1) affecting the production of goods, (2) affecting the utility from consumers, (3) affecting both, and (4) affecting the welfare function using damage functions.

These four approaches represent different modeling strategies for incorporating biodiversity's direct effects into economic functions. While they appear as distinct categories from a modeling implementation perspective, they are conceptually interconnected, given the inherent linkages between production, consumption, and welfare in economic theory. Impacts on one component will indirectly affect the others.

When affecting the production of goods, a well-known example is the use of Natural Capital (Barbier 2019, Bateman and Mace 2020, Dasgupta 2021), which intends to extend the concept of produced capital and human capital, to include natural capital as a factor of production in the economy. Connecting biodiversity to the production of goods represents the dependence of the economic system on functioning ecosystems that provide us with the means and climate stability to gather raw materials and transform them into economic goods. In this way, affecting the production of goods represents market use values

of biodiversity. Equation (2), taken from Dasgupta (2021), represents how the natural capital concept attempts to represent the participation of nature in the global economy,

$$Y = AS^\beta K^a H^b R^{(1-a-b)} \quad (2)$$

where Y refers to produced economic output, that can be consumed or invested, K is produced capital, H is human capital, and A publicly available knowledge (also called *Total Factor Productivity*). Natural capital is represented via two components, S the stock that supplies regulating and maintenance services (e.g. carbon and nitrogen cycles, climate regulation, soil regeneration) in the form of a public good, and R as the flow of extracted provisioning services (e.g. fish, usable water, timber, food, etc). Here $\beta > 0; a, b, (1 - a - b) > 0$ represent the elasticities of production with respect to each input of production. A more detailed discussion about how biodiversity could be represented using Natural capital and rules of thumb to follow suggested guiding principles can be found in Bateman and Mace (2020). A different approach affects production by affecting the productivity of a specific economic sector (e.g. agricultural productivity) as a function of the level of ecosystem services provided, as has been done by Johnson *et al* (2020, 2023a). In this case, using InVEST, a pollinators' abundance indicator is calculated to estimate a pollination sufficiency indicator on a spatial explicit level. With this pollination sufficiency indicator, a proportional change in effective hectares p_c for each crop c is calculated. Then, using a pollination yield dependency ratio d_c , a change in production efficiency for each crop e_c is calculated as shown in equation (3).

$$e_c = p_c \times d_c \quad (3)$$

Practical challenges when affecting production functions is how to calibrate elasticities (e.g. β, a, b in equation (2)) and to represent how changes in biodiversity affect productivity. For the former, structural parametric estimation can be considered. The latter is in general a major challenge since for implementation purposes, the relationship between biodiversity and each type of relevant ecosystem service (provisioning, regulating, or maintenance) needs to be represented for the economic sector of interest. This is particularly difficult because the loss of a species alters both species richness (number of species) and community composition (which species). Consequently, the impact on ecosystem services depends on the degree to which different species' functional traits can substitute for one another (Weiskopf *et al* 2022). More information on the challenge to connect biodiversity and ecosystem services can be found in the supplementary section S4. Still, the connection of biodiversity with some economic sectors can be currently represented. For example, the connection between the

agricultural sector and pollinators' biodiversity, as described before, or how crop yields are affected as a response to plants' species richness (Johnson *et al* 2020, 2021, 2023a, Pamuk *et al* 2023).

The next approach consists of extending the utility functions of consumers. An example of this approach is that of Eichner and Pethig (2006) who represented consumers for whom their utility depends on consumption, ecosystem services, and biodiversity, as shown in equation (4).

$$u = U(y_c, \bar{r} - r_y, n_1, n_2, n_3) \quad (4)$$

where utility for the representative consumer depends both on the consumption of consumer good y_c and on ecosystem services. The latter are assumed to be positively correlated with both the size of the habitat left for non-human species $\bar{r} - r_y$ and the populations of all the non-human species included n_1, n_2, n_3 . Fenichel *et al* (2024) describes in detail the difference and consequences between including n_1, n_2, n_3 populations explicitly in the utility function or using a biodiversity index that aggregates them, given that each n_i is determined by interactions between all the species in the ecosystem. However, because this approach requires selecting specific species, based for example on specific geographies, social and economic conditions, it may be better suited to sectoral or more regional analyses.

Other examples of modifying the utility function include (Bastien-Olvera and Moore 2021) and BLUE RICE (Bastien-Olvera *et al* 2026). These examples have instead modified the utility function by including a use and non-use value component (see equation (5)). The former includes both economic output (C) and ecosystem services (ES), and the latter includes the non-use value (*NonUse*) attributed to specific ecosystems. In this case both a valuation of non-market ecosystem services and non-use value derived from biodiversity are required,

$$u = U(Use, NonUse) \quad (5)$$

$$Use = f(C, ES). \quad (6)$$

Affecting the utility function will reflect how much humans in the economic system care or value ecosystems. This could represent both use value and non-use value. Use value in this case refers to non-market use value, for example associated to cultural services (which include spiritual and religious values, knowledge system, education and inspiration, recreation and aesthetic values, and sense of place (Millenium Ecosystem Assessment 2005)). Non-use value instead refers to the value given to the existence of ecosystems and natural systems without considering any use or consumption (existence value, bequest value⁸). The main practical challenge for this

⁸ Value of preserving the resource for future generations.

approach is the parametrization of the utility functions, in particular regarding the level of substitutability between consumption, biodiversity, and or ecosystem services. The latter can be addressed using different scenarios varying the elasticities of substitution and therefore showing the sensitivity of the results to this assumption.

When affecting both production and utility functions, both the effects of degraded ecosystems and biodiversity loss in the production of goods, and the effects in how humans value nature are being represented.

An additional approach applicable to macro-economic models with a centralized approach (i.e. a central planner doing welfare maximization) is to affect the welfare function. This can be done by adding an additional term, such as the welfare cost per unit of biodiversity loss or through damage functions. These damage functions represent changes in welfare (typically measured with GDP) as a response to changes in a variable of interest. For climate change damage functions, these typically show changes in GDP as a response to temperature changes, which are then used to affect net economic output, and consequently consumption. Similar implementations can be done estimating a damage function of welfare in response to ecosystems' status or biodiversity. These damage functions are estimated with statistical methods. A major practical challenge is that of solving potential endogeneity issues. Similarly, there is a problem with scale when estimating these functions. Some economic sectors may benefit, while others, may be negatively affected by biodiversity loss. As a consequence, both the net effect on the economy may be small, making the identification of the effect difficult, but also obscuring heterogeneous effects between economic sectors and spatial locations.

To be noted is that all four approaches require information on the relationship between the biodiversity indicator and the economy. This implies requirements on functional forms and their parameters. So far, current literature has used a empirical methods to derive them.

As can be noted most existing approaches use ecosystem services as a means to integrate biodiversity in the economic system instead of using biodiversity indicators directly. This has led some studies to skip the use of biodiversity indicators, arguing this is what really affects the economic system. However, it is important to acknowledge that biodiversity is not the same as ecosystem services, implying that making decisions only considering changes in ecosystem services may not result in achieving conservation targets for biodiversity.

4.3. Integrated approaches

The previous sections described possible methodological approaches for each direction of the biodiversity-economy link in IAMs. The selected

approach to improve the representation of biodiversity in an IAM will depend on the type of IAM, on the drivers represented, on its spatial resolution, on the economic representation of agents (centralized vs decentralized), and data availability, among others.

Following previous integrations of other systems models, for example, land or climate systems, the integration of biodiversity in IAMs can be thought of as an additional module for the IAM as represented by the diagram in figure 5. This new module will take as input information about the drivers of biodiversity loss, estimate biodiversity impacts, and provide the information required for the economic system, according to the integration of the second direction of the link used.

Still, challenges remain with the integration of the two directions. First, there are differences in the spatial scale under which biodiversity indicators and ecosystems' status are assessed and the scale of the economic system represented in IAMs. To harmonize spatial scale differences, we described two main approaches, *aggregating* gridded information into regions to endogenize decisions in the IAM, or *disaggregate* IAM results for post-processing analysis. Both have their advantages and limitations. Second, various integration options rely on the link between biodiversity and the provision of ecosystem services, for which no general well-understood mathematical relationship exists. Moreover, this relationship will depend on the location, ecosystem service, and economic sector, making generalizations difficult, especially for IAMs without sectoral differentiation. More information about the connection between biodiversity and ecosystem services can be found in supplementary section S4.

5. Conclusion

In the context of a dual biodiversity and climate crisis, integrated models that represent their interconnections will allow for a more comprehensive policy analysis. Improving the modeling representation of biodiversity in IAMs is important to consider biodiversity implications of climate policy, and to assess more comprehensive mitigation pathways that consider conservation policies that aim to bend the curve on biodiversity loss. In this paper, we focus on describing the current state of the art about the modeling representation of biodiversity in IAMs and propose practical directions of improvement, considering a broader set of literature.

Representing biodiversity in IAMs is not the only way to integrate models for climate change and biodiversity loss. Other approaches—for example, integrating climate policy or economic models with more detailed biodiversity or ecosystem models—are also valuable. We acknowledge these alternative paradigms but they are beyond the scope of this paper.

Considering a double link between biodiversity and the economy, we identified that due to structural and historical reasons, Detailed-process IAMs and Reduced-form IAMs have been interested in different types of biodiversity related questions. Detailed-process IAMs have been more focused on representing the impacts on biodiversity of different socio-economic scenarios, which relates to a better representation of impacts on biodiversity from economic decisions (i.e. the link from the economic system to ecosystems). Instead, Reduced-form IAMs have been more focused on the impacts on human well-being of biodiversity loss due to climate change, using damage functions to represent the effects of ecosystem degradation in the economic system (i.e. the link from ecosystems to the economic system). Given how the literature in the representation of biodiversity between the two types has diverged, we separated the description of the state of the art in this review.

We collected and reviewed 38 papers that represented biodiversity in IAMs, from which 32 are associated with Detailed-process IAMs and 6 with Reduced-form IAMs. The difference in the number of papers using Detailed-process IAMs versus Reduced-form IAMs reflects how Detailed-process IAMs have focused more on this integration.

To describe the current state of the art, we defined 5 dimensions to describe the representation

of biodiversity in the models: (1) if it represents biodiversity or ecosystem services, (2) which are the drivers of biodiversity loss included, (3) the type of modeling approach, (4) if the representation is endogenous or post-processing and (5) the spatial scale.

We described modeling gaps separating them according to each direction of the link between biodiversity and the economic system. Regarding the representation of biodiversity impacts, both types of IAMs need to include additional drivers. Detailed-process IAMs have mainly focused on habitat loss and climate change, whereas Reduced-form IAMs have only considered mean temperature as a proxy of climate change. In this way, pollutants, invasive species and overexploitation are still missing. Detailed-process IAMs also need to improve the representation of habitat quality and structure by considering other characteristics beyond habitat area and to better address the uncertainty of biodiversity models (Thuiller *et al* 2019). Moreover, more than one biodiversity indicator should be used. This is particularly important due to the multidimensionality of the biodiversity concept, it helps to address uncertainty and its impact on policy making. Reduced-form IAMs major gap is the lack of representation of biodiversity indicators and in particular the lack of use of spatial explicit information that represents regional differences. Currently relying on functions calibrated with 'expert guesses'

or previous literature, Reduced-form IAMs may be potentially misrepresenting the impacts on biodiversity, turning this into a major area for improvement. Furthermore, all studies focused on terrestrial ecosystems, leaving out freshwater and marine ecosystems.

Regarding the representation of how ecosystems status affects decisions in the economic system, Detailed-process IAMs should concentrate on establishing this relationship since all studies except one have done a post-processing analysis of biodiversity. Reduced-form IAMs instead should focus on a better calibration of the functions that associate biodiversity impacts to ecosystem services.

All these gaps and suggested improvements align with the previous challenges and research frontiers identified by Rosa *et al* (2020) and Chaplin-Kramer *et al* (2024). In particular, if the gaps identified here are addressed, for example using the proposed methodologies in sections 4.1 and 4.2, we will be a step further in improving the representation of drivers in the scenarios, expanding the coverage of multiple dimensions of biodiversity, and representing the connection between biodiversity and ecosystem services. This would require concentrated efforts on improving the calibration and validation of biodiversity and ecosystem service models using historical data. By doing so, we will be progressing on linking the ecological impacts to human well-being and incorporating the feedbacks of ecosystem services on the socio-economic system in IAMs.

Future efforts to improve the representation of biodiversity in IAMs, can face practical limitations. For example, IAMs that do not yet have a representation of the land system, will be unable to connect with existing biodiversity models. For those IAMs lacking sectoral representation, representing how biodiversity status can affect production will be challenging, since implementations similar to those done by Johnson *et al* (2020) cannot be yet explored. Moreover, the lack of data availability and coverage to properly fit and validate functions that relate drivers to biodiversity, biodiversity to ecosystem services, and ecosystem services to human well-being is still a limiting factor. For the latter, artificial intelligence appears as a promising tool to improve existing biodiversity datasets (Pollock *et al* 2025) and modeling such relationships.

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Data availability statement

All data that support the findings of this study are included within the article (and any supplementary files).

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